

A Comparison of Statistical and Neural Machine Translation for Slovene, Serbian and Croatian

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sentence one with some words
sentence two with more words
...

stavek ena z nekaj besedami
stavek dva z več besed ...
...

Word Embeddings

slovenian 0.157417 0.013155 -0.168669 0.258004 -0.261520 -0.004266 0.064963 -0.095019 0.110000
0.139827 -0.009515 0.102139 -0.014292 0.064913 0.116374 -0.248112 -0.179980 0.143360 -0.058822 -
0.081025 -0.204884 0.024653 -0.008157 -0.208811 -0.351810 -0.020040 -0.191807 -0.004969 0.148161
-0.124785 0.073630 -0.063658 -0.325918 0.170596 0.123046 0.106464 -0.141023 0.037222 0.095813
0.349635 0.166654 -0.160324 -0.036104 0.016911 0.002022 0.026284 -0.129991 -0.061656 0.075007 -
0.200100 -0.026334 -0.169233 0.033682 0.031311 0.034157 -0.056466 -0.010009 0.373934 -0.461444
0.137428 -0.080984 -0.214958 0.133438 -0.206060 -0.044642 -0.020855 0.001350 -0.032700 0.054392
-0.138733 0.271986 0.074465 -0.383632 -0.060489 0.170901 -0.007525 -0.213951 -0.215574 -0.237169
0.047382 0.059949 -0.167393 -0.086040 0.037600 -0.064871 0.099520 -0.137147 0.170327 -0.044044
0.238244 0.082285 -0.030852 0.061542 -0.099835 -0.154609 -0.162004 0.061578 -0.172150 -0.163639
-0.012122 -0.085171 0.197971 0.483274 0.020190 0.203729 0.267945 -0.159703 -0.352687 0.009871
0.032857 0.076368 0.090400 0.143115 0.161378 -0.203485 -0.020512 -0.139726 0.174444 -0.035236
0.069389 0.157347 -0.254437 0.016946 -0.190948 -0.186738 0.060985 0.376371 -0.084888 -0.330832 -
0.032036 0.072837 -0.381461 0.088491 -0.315386 0.119776 -0.174684 0.337164 0.031623 0.036908
0.297419 -0.208412 0.316575 0.036308 0.119306 -0.025103 0.110816 -0.072111 -0.197073 0.154872
0.285448 0.063191 -0.018339 -0.117289 -0.089172 0.033924 -0.297626 -0.094350 -0.106417 -0.283593
-0.126537 0.131320 -0.087875 -0.044319 -0.143214 -0.086091 0.147566 0.043141 -0.121772 -0.123281
-0.044752 0.036134 -0.273063 -0.046211 0.014122 -0.001258 0.216371 0.027509 -0.117638 0.249159
0.137707 0.087296 0.059431 0.029131 -0.079217 0.007073 0.006122 -0.015539 0.112570 0.250844 -
0.012353 -0.162030 -0.107101 0.072732 -0.159938 0.064535 0.069997 0.155462 -0.015620 0.390249
0.096999

... Machine Translation for Slovene, Serbian and Croatian

META-NET Language White Paper Series (2012)

Machine Translation

Excellent support	Good support	Moderate support	Fragmentary support	Weak/no support
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">English	<ul style="list-style-type: none">FrenchSpanish	<ul style="list-style-type: none">CatalanDutchGermanHungarianItalianPolishRomanian	<ul style="list-style-type: none">BasqueBulgarianCroatianCzechDanishEstonianFinnishGalicianGreekIcelandicIrishLatvianLithuanianMalteseNorwegian (Bokmål, Nynorsk)PortugueseSerbianSlovakSloveneSwedishWelsh

each hard capsule contains 182.2 mg of anhydrous lactose .

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infections at the injection site (including abscess and cellulitis) occurred in 1.5 % of patients .

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Byte Pair Encoding (BPE)

Sentence	Tokenised Sentence	BPE Segmented Sentence
procedures for proper handling and disposal of antineoplastic medicinal products should be used.	procedures for proper handling and disposal of antineoplastic medicinal products should be used .	procedures for proper handling and disposal of ant ■ ine ■ op ■ lastic medicinal products should be used ■ .
many thanks to mrs van lancker, mr berman, mr lambsdorff, mr hutchinson, mrs scheele, mrs doyle, mrs weber, mr varvitsiotis, mrs hassi and mrs gomes.	many thanks to mrs van lancker , mr berman , mr lambsdorff , mr hutchinson , mrs scheele , mrs doyle , mrs weber , mr varvitsiotis , mrs hassi and mrs gomes .	many thanks to mrs van lanc ■ ker ■ , mr berman ■ , mr lamb ■ s ■ dor ■ ff ■ , mr hut ■ chin ■ son ■ , mrs sche ■ ele ■ , mrs doyle ■ , mrs weber ■ , mr var ■ vit ■ si ■ otis ■ , mrs hass ■ i and mrs g ■ omes ■ .
kdo vam daje pravico, da invalidom odrekate neomejen dostop do izobraževanja, ali da starejšim ljudem odrekate enako obravnavo pri zavarovanjih in finančnih storitvah?	kdo vam daje pravico , da invalidom odrekate neomejen dostop do izobraževanja , ali da starejšim ljudem odrekate enako obravnavo pri zavarovanjih in finančnih storitvah ?	kdo vam daje pravico ■ , da invali ■ dom odre ■ kate ne ■ omejen dostop do izo- braževanja ■ , ali da stare ■ jšim ljudem odre ■ kate enako obravnavo pri zavarov ■ anjih in finančnih storitvah ■ ?

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Initial Experiments

—●— En-SI NMT random sent. (50k) —+— En-SI NMT random sent. (BPE32k)
—+— En-SI NMT relevant sent. (50k) —●— En-SI NMT relevant sent. (BPE32k)

SMT

Moses (phrase based alignment)
Giza++ (word alignment)
KenLM (language model)

NMT

OpenNMT
(500/600/1000/
dimensions, 2/4
layers, bidirectional
LSTM)

Evaluation

BLEU (Papineni et al., 2002)
Meteor (Denkowski and Lavie, 2014)
chrF (Popović, 2015)

Datasets (Related sentences)

	L1 Lang.	-	L2 Lang.	L1 Language			L2 Language	
				Sentences	Tokens	Types	Tokens	Types
Training Dataset	English	-	Slovene	2,299,805	37,849,280	631,114	33,379,920	587,018
	English	-	Croatian	2,464,895	34,880,415	626,353	29,744,620	593,672
	English	-	Serbian	2,152,740	27,465,108	658,660	23,536,540	573,241
	Croatian	-	Serbian	2,177,242	22,717,151	1,200,577	22,790,166	1,170,801
	Slovene	-	Croatian	2,004,229	17,759,047	464,392	18,150,733	545,023
	Slovene	-	Serbian	2,131,301	20,515,466	769,019	21,257,242	883,175
Development Dataset	English	-	Slovene	2,017	38,280	32,918	10,092	13,650
	English	-	Croatian	2,114	45,605	40,536	8,264	12,638
	English	-	Serbian	2,092	37,757	35,419	10,373	14,017
	Croatian	-	Serbian	2,000	14,716	14,774	4,601	4,620
	Slovene	-	Croatian	2,000	14,339	14,447	3,924	4,215
	Slovene	-	Serbian	2,000	12,985	13,575	3,890	4,060
Evaluation Dataset	English	-	Slovene	2,015	44,559	39,561	7,414	10,972
	English	-	Croatian	2,113	45,768	40,462	8,218	12,727
	English	-	Serbian	2,036	40,349	37,346	6,833	10,866
	Croatian	-	Serbian	2,000	12,805	13,043	3,909	3,984
	Slovene	-	Croatian	2,000	13,799	14,187	3,794	4,109
	Slovene	-	Serbian	2,000	13,090	13,606	3,900	4,138

Evaluation (Related sentences)

	SMT			NMT		
	BLEU	Meteor	chrF	BLEU	Meteor	chrF
English → Slovene	37.35	29.92	60.74	27.41	24.83	53.02
Slovene → English	46.02	37.42	64.61	27.80	29.28	52.76
English → Croatian	32.44	28.03	57.46	20.94	21.69	49.73
Croatian → English	37.49	35.26	60.66	23.73	26.67	50.41
English → Serbian	31.30	27.33	55.28	17.44	20.24	45.89
Serbian → English	32.49	34.18	57.82	20.64	25.00	48.02
Slovene → Serbian	19.37	22.09	41.52	19.95	21.35	40.99
Serbian → Slovene	21.51	22.82	43.46	21.68	22.30	43.10
Slovene → Croatian	21.29	22.93	43.97	19.54	21.01	40.60
Croatian → Slovene	25.94	25.39	47.60	24.77	24.12	45.71
Serbian → Croatian	68.96	48.24	79.96	61.06	42.76	76.85
Croatian → Serbian	68.15	46.70	78.14	64.25	43.84	76.83

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Experiments on Compressed Data

	2M		
	Sentences	Tokens	Types
random (English)	2,000,000	25,496,017	243,512
random (Slovene)	2,000,000	21,175,388	415,965
compressed (English)	2,299,805	37,849,280	631,114
compressed (Slovene)	2,299,805	33,379,920	587,018
	5M		
	Sentences	Tokens	Types
random (English)	4,980,012	61,802,915	386,260
random (Slovene)	4,980,012	51,219,305	640,471
compressed (English)	5,003,508	85,675,760	618,112
compressed (Slovene)	5,003,508	72,868,553	964,763

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Evaluation on Compressed Data and different architecture

	2M			2M++		
<u>English → Slovene</u>	BLEU	Meteor	chrF	BLEU	Meteor	chrF
random	35.49	29.47	60.52	35.26	29.27	59.52
compressed	27.41	24.83	53.02	29.30	25.75	54.51
<u>Slovene → English</u>	BLEU	Meteor	chrF	BLEU	Meteor	chrF
random	38.77	35.29	61.15	36.86	33.90	59.31
compressed	27.80	29.28	52.76	28.76	29.53	53.19
	5M			5M++		
<u>English → Slovene</u>	BLEU	Meteor	chrF	BLEU	Meteor	chrF
random	36.60	29.94	60.33	38.01	30.75	61.54
compressed	37.56	30.57	61.75	38.75	31.19	62.58
<u>Slovene → English</u>	BLEU	Meteor	chrF	BLEU	Meteor	chrF
random	36.72	33.90	59.58	38.02	34.08	59.70
compressed	37.71	34.38	60.09	40.30	35.61	62.16

Evaluation on Compressed Data and different architecture

	2M			2M++		
<u>English → Slovene</u>	BLEU	Meteor	chrF	BLEU	Meteor	chrF
random	35.49	29.47	60.52	35.26	29.27	59.52
compressed	27.41	24.83	53.02	29.30	25.75	54.51
<u>Slovene → English</u>	BLEU	Meteor	chrF	BLEU	Meteor	chrF
random	38.77	35.29	61.15	36.86	33.90	59.31
compressed	27.80	29.28	52.76	28.76	29.53	53.19
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<u>Slovene → English</u>	BLEU	Meteor	chrF	BLEU	Meteor	chrF
random	36.72	33.90	59.58	38.02	34.08	59.70
compressed	37.71	34.38	60.09	40.30	35.61	62.16

Evaluation on Compressed Data and different architecture

	2M			2M++		
<u>English → Slovene</u>	BLEU	Meteor	chrF	BLEU	Meteor	chrF
random	35.49	29.47	60.52	35.26	29.27	59.52
compressed	27.41	24.83	53.02	29.30	25.75	54.51
<u>Slovene → English</u>	BLEU	Meteor	chrF	BLEU	Meteor	chrF
random	38.77	35.29	61.15	36.86	33.90	59.31
compressed	27.80	29.28	52.76	28.76	29.53	53.19
	5M			5M++		
<u>English → Slovene</u>	BLEU	Meteor	chrF	BLEU	Meteor	chrF
random	36.60	29.94	60.33	38.01	30.75	61.54
compressed	37.56	30.57	61.75	38.75	31.19	62.58
<u>Slovene → English</u>	BLEU	Meteor	chrF	BLEU	Meteor	chrF
random	36.72	33.90	59.58	38.02	34.08	59.70
compressed	37.71	34.38	60.09	40.30	35.61	62.16

Evaluation on Compressed Data and different architecture

	2M			2M++		
<u>English → Slovene</u>	BLEU	Meteor	chrF	BLEU	Meteor	chrF
random	35.49	29.47	60.52	35.26	29.27	59.52
compressed	27.41	24.83	53.02	29.30	25.75	54.51
<u>Slovene → English</u>	BLEU	Meteor	chrF	BLEU	Meteor	chrF
random	38.77	35.29	61.15	36.86	33.90	59.31
compressed	27.80	29.28	52.76	28.76	29.53	53.19
	5M			5M++		
<u>English → Slovene</u>	BLEU	Meteor	chrF	BLEU	Meteor	chrF
random	36.60	29.94	60.33	38.01	30.75	61.54
compressed	37.56	30.57	61.75	38.75	31.19	62.58
<u>Slovene → English</u>	BLEU	Meteor	chrF	BLEU	Meteor	chrF
random	36.72	33.90	59.58	38.02	34.08	59.70
compressed	37.71	34.38	60.09	40.30	35.61	62.16

Evaluation on Compressed Data and different architecture

	2M			2M++		
<u>English → Slovene</u>	BLEU	Meteor	chrF	BLEU	Meteor	chrF
random	35.49	29.47	60.52	35.26	29.27	59.52
compressed	27.41	24.83	53.02	29.30	25.75	54.51
<u>Slovene → English</u>	BLEU	Meteor	chrF	BLEU	Meteor	chrF
random	38.77	35.29	61.15	36.86	33.90	59.31
compressed	27.80	29.28	52.76	28.76	29.53	53.19
	5M			5M++		
<u>English → Slovene</u>	BLEU	Meteor	chrF	BLEU	Meteor	chrF
random	36.60	29.94	60.33	38.01	30.75	61.54
compressed	37.56	30.57	61.75	38.75	31.19	62.58
<u>Slovene → English</u>	BLEU	Meteor	chrF	BLEU	Meteor	chrF
random	36.72	33.90	59.58	38.02	34.08	59.70
compressed	37.71	34.38	60.09	40.30	35.61	62.16

Comparison between different SMT and NMT methods

- better understanding and evaluation
- NMT for an under-resourced scenario
- multiway models

The screenshot shows the ASISTENT web interface. At the top, the logo 'ASISTENT' is followed by 'English-Slavic Translation System'. Navigation links include Home, About, Team, Docker, and Other Projects. The main content area is split into two columns. The left column contains a text input field with the instruction 'Add text to be translated and specify the translation direction:'. Above the input are four buttons: 'English Example', 'Slovene Example', 'Croatian Example', and 'Serbian Example'. Below the input is a 'Translate' button. The right column contains a description of the system and a list of translation options. The footer includes logos for Insight, NUI Galway OE Gaillimh, and SFI, along with a funding notice.

ASISTENT English-Slavic Translation System

Home About Team Docker Other Projects

Add text to be translated and specify the translation direction:

English Example Slovene Example Croatian Example Serbian Example

Translate

This service is brought to you by <http://nuig.insight-centre.org/unlp/>

ASISTENT (or `assistant@en`) was developed to translate text between English and the morphological complex south Slavic languages: Slovene, Serbian and Croatian.

Select translation option/approach:

- phrase based hierarchical neural
- direct translation pivot translation

Please choose the translation direction:

- English → Slovene Slovene → English
- English → Croatian Croatian → English
- English → Serbian Serbian → English
- Slovene → Croatian Croatian → Slovene
- Serbian → Slovene Slovene → Serbian
- Croatian → Serbian Serbian → Croatian

Insight NUI Galway OE Gaillimh sfi

This resource has been funded by Grant No. SFI/12/RC/2289 - INSIGHT - National University of Ireland, Galway

<http://server1.nlp.insight-centre.org/asistent/>

A Comparison of Statistical and Neural Machine Translation for Slovene, Serbian and Croatian

Mihael Arcan

mihael.arcan@insight-centre.org

Thank You

Comparison of different RNNs

	English-Irish		English-Basque	
	Word	BPE	Word	BPE
RNN	48.78	49.39	38.07	26.57
bidirectional RNN	50.99	51.6	40.43	27.88
Deep bidirectional RNN	51.42	52.44	41.37	28.21
Pyramidal Deep bidirectional RNN	49.78	50.78	40.42	27.76
GNMT (transformer)	50.15	50.87	39.27	27.22

	BLEU	Meteor	chrF
Slovene-Serbian	5.30	11.48	25.61
Serbian-Slovene	5.24	11.97	26.61
Slovene-Croatian	4.80	11.51	26.34
Croatian-Slovene	4.76	11.98	27.80
Serbian-Croatian	66.78	46.70	78.53
Croatian-Serbian	67.20	46.08	77.85

	SMT			NMT		
	BLEU	Meteor	chrF	BLEU	Meteor	chrF
Slovene → Serbian	19.37	22.09	41.52	19.95	21.35	40.99
Serbian → Slovene	21.51	22.82	43.46	21.68	22.30	43.10
Slovene → Croatian	21.29	22.93	43.97	19.54	21.01	40.60
Croatian → Slovene	25.94	25.39	47.60	24.77	24.12	45.71
Serbian → Croatian	68.96	48.24	79.96	61.06	42.76	76.85
Croatian → Serbian	68.15	46.70	78.14	64.25	43.84	76.83

Multiway Models experiments

	500k				2M			
	2/500/500		4/600/1000		2/500/500		4/600/1000	
	Word	BPE	Word	BPE	Word	BPE	Word	BPE
En-Sl	6.37	3.54	7.28	5.8	11.11	6.63	11.77	8.14
Sl-En	10.29	3.18	8.65	5.04	13.77	7.88	13.77	7.01
En-Sr	7.56	4.2	6.2	3.25	10.22	3.83	9.15	6.83
Sr-En	10.26	7.67	7.23	5.98	14.32	11.21	13.9	11.87
En-Hr	6.66	3.97	5.75	3.99	9.67	2.4	9.09	6.76
Hr-En	8.55	7.21	9.18	6.37	13.18	9.78	13.2	8.96
Sl-Sr	15.66	7.08	14.58	7.14	10.99	18.25	9.14	18.35
Sr-Sl	18.22	13.8	17.56	11.34	21.38	17.22	21.02	15.96
Sl-Hr	16.98	10	16.33	10.14	19.25	12.1	19.43	13.14
Hr-Sl	18.96	12.84	18.37	12.74	21.99	16.92	21.26	13.62
Sr-Hr	56.28	44.76	53.6	52.61	58.71	53.75	58.56	54.25
Hr-Sr	54.13	43.24	52.11	41.3	56.26	52.23	55.95	51.34

All available data vs 2M parallel data

	SMT		
	BLEU	Meteor	chrF
English → Slovene	37.35	29.92	60.74
Slovene → English	46.02	37.42	64.61
English → Croatian	32.44	28.03	57.46
Croatian → English	37.49	35.26	60.66
English → Serbian	31.30	27.33	55.28
Serbian → English	32.49	34.18	57.82
Slovene → Serbian	19.37	22.09	41.52
Serbian → Slovene	21.51	22.82	43.46
Slovene → Croatian	21.29	22.93	43.97
Croatian → Slovene	25.94	25.39	47.60
Serbian → Croatian	68.96	48.24	79.96
Croatian → Serbian	68.15	46.70	78.14

	English → Slovene			Slovene → English		
	BLEU	Meteor	chrF3	BLEU	Meteor	chrF3
Google	34.46	32.90	61.75	44.41	40.59	62.94
Asistent	49.82	36.36	69.26	64.14	45.77	76.71
	English → Croatian			Croatian → English		
	BLEU	Meteor	chrF3	BLEU	Meteor	chrF3
Google	29.27	26.87	57.19	46.08	39.35	67.61
Asistent	42.15	33.02	64.95	48.07	40.05	68.18
	English → Serbian			Serbian → English		
	BLEU	Meteor	chrF3	BLEU	Meteor	chrF3
Google	27.48	26.33	55.80	46.05	39.35	67.53
Asistent	42.47	32.63	63.59	42.35	39.11	64.96
	Slovene → Serbian			Serbian → Slovene		
	BLEU	Meteor	chrF3	BLEU	Meteor	chrF3
Google	12.27	16.83	34.27	14.05	18.32	37.16
Asistent	23.46	23.23	43.23	29.23	25.33	47.42
	Croatian → Serbian			Serbian → Croatian		
	BLEU	Meteor	chrF3	BLEU	Meteor	chrF3
Google	59.88	41.72	73.84	64.90	46.11	78.65
Asistent	67.39	46.34	77.98	70.09	48.97	80.89
	Slovene → Croatian			Croatian → Slovene		
	BLEU	Meteor	chrF3	BLEU	Meteor	chrF3
Google	13.47	17.81	37.36	16.07	19.60	39.54
Asistent	34.63	27.02	50.98	38.64	29.78	54.98